

Eco-Friendly Pest Management in Vegetable Farming: IPDM Practices and Adoption Constraints

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Integrated Pest and Disease Management (IPDM) is a sustainable and ecologically sound approach that combines multiple control strategies to manage pests and diseases below economic threshold levels. In vegetable crops, which are highly susceptible to a range of pests and pathogens due to their tender foliage, short lifecycle, and intensive cultivation, IPDM plays a crucial role in ensuring yield stability and food safety. Traditional reliance on chemical pesticides has led to problems such as pest resistance, environmental pollution, and residues in produce. IPDM addresses these challenges by integrating biological control agents, cultural practices, resistant varieties, mechanical tools, and need-based chemical applications. Implementation of IPDM in vegetable farming has shown promising results in managing pests like fruit borers, aphids, whiteflies, and diseases such as blights, wilts, and mildews. However, adoption remains limited due to inadequate farmer training, lack of awareness, and insufficient availability of eco-friendly inputs. The situation is further complicated by climate change, which alters pest dynamics and disease epidemiology, requiring adaptive and location-specific IPDM strategies. Recent innovations, including pheromone traps, neem-based biopesticides, and mobile-based advisory systems, have improved accessibility and effectiveness of IPDM in vegetable crops. To maximize impact, capacity-building programs, policy incentives, and farmer-friendly technologies must be promoted. With proper implementation, IPDM offers a pathway to sustainable vegetable production, minimizing environmental impact while safeguarding human health.

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